

ACCENTUATION FOR TEENAGERS

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Abstract. Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, characterized by its peculiarities from physiological and psychological humor. At this stage, the physical and psychic development of children is greatly accelerated, interest in various things in life, desire for novelty increases, character is formed, the spiritual world is enriched, conflicts are escalated. adolescence is a period of puberty and is also characterized by the emergence of new Hiss, sensations and tangled issues related to sexual behavior.

Key words: adolescence, psychophysiological, process accentuation, diagnostic, cognitive-affective, interview methods, the experiment psychology.

АКЦЕНТУАЦИЯ ДЛЯ ПОДРОСТКОВ

Аннотация. Подростковый возраст – это период перехода от детства к взрослой жизни, характеризующийся своими особенностями со стороны физиологического и психологического юмора. На этом этапе значительно ускоряется физическое и психическое развитие детей, повышается интерес к разным вещам в жизни, стремление к новизне, формируется характер, обогащается духовный мир, обостряются конфликты. подростковый возраст является периодом полового созревания и также характеризуется появлением новых шипений, ощущений и запутанных вопросов, связанных с сексуальным поведением.

Ключевые слова: подростковый возраст, психофизиологический, процесс акцентирования, диагностический, когнитивно-аффективный, методы интервью, психология эксперимента.

Age limit the age range to 10-15 teenage currently into right comes. Every teenage appearances in character called will be different. This feature of the character he or quantitative expressiveness left to go when the last of the last finish most of the character limit and norms accentuation (excessive emphasis be given) is called. Excessive emphasis be given some character features as the result of the escalation of character the last option is believed to be one of the norm. In this case, there is an increase in weakness to the same stlaessogenic (strongly excitatory) factors in the individual, while there is stability in relation to others. It is possible that the accentuation of the character leads to pathological disorders and changes in personality behavior, psychopathy in extremely inappropriate situations (a pathology in which the character is an obstacle to adequate social adaptation of the individual and is practically not tachylarized, although some corrections are given in the right treatment conditions), but it is inappropriate to consider it.

The classification of types of accentuation (over – emphasis) of a character is much more complicated and does not overlap in different nomenclature. (K.Léongard, A.Lichko). But the description of the accentuated features remains to some extent the same. This is both the terminology and the classification scheme psychiatric successful in terminology ("the properties of schizophrenia", "epilepsy" features, etc.) without direct similarities with excessive emphasis he gives a list of features which give you the opportunity to bring final. The assessment of character with excessive emphasis requires the attention of a pedagogue, not a psychiatrist, although the

history of the problem of accentuation on average goes back to psychiatry and psychoneurology. Adolescence – the transition period from childhood into big is characterized by specific physiological and psychological intraoperative features. At this stage of the child's physical development is greatly accelerated and psychic in life is to be interested in different things, newsletter aspiration increases, the character is in the form of the spiritual world will enrich, gets the culmination of the conflict. Teenages adolescence period is reached, the new feeling and confused the issue with the appearance of life is characterized relate to sexual sensations.

Without a study of psychological characteristics that are specific to the age of adolescence, teenagers progressing form of the person, to identities and developing ways to reach and understand the importance of the direct impact of biological and social factors that influenced him, we can. A teenager with a happy childhood but in this era failed to find its place in adult life is not as complicated xayirlashgan xali. Therefore, the period of adolescence “transition period”, “period of crisis” (crisis), “a delicately period”, “difficult period”, “the puberty period,” as it is characterized by the appearances of psychological received the name. The appearance of an aggressive attitude towards adults on adolescent skin, such as negativism, is not only signs that arise due to direct sexual maturation, from which unpleasant signs of behavior spontaneously arise, but also through the means of social conditions in which the teenager lives, which indirectly affects them: his peers, status in the community, relationship with adults, character traits that arise In adolescence, the leading activity is reading, communication and cocktail activities. The main task of adolescence the period of this communication, friendship, and the fundamental norms of physics is to identify. The main feature of communication that it iboratkı of friendship teenagers are subject to the full code.

Teenagers differentiation different things absolutely clear. You stand and put a chair during the break he broke her fix should be in play workshops, this is not a punishment. If this is not a punishment forced to sweep his location also made you dirty. Teenager logic for this is obvious: this is not punishment, but the letter is to correct the results of actions.

Psychology spiritual consciousness before their teenagers to the content of the concept of ethics and their idea of ‘rga were put to use the function. In general, studies show that teenagers at a high level of spiritual consciousness. The majority of teenagers did not understand the spiritual part of a worthy concepts to properly age. Provide a few examples. assertiveness is" a trait that is seen when a person sets out to do the most difficult things, without fear of what failure Hech takes the job to the end "(12th) " decisiveness also develops in a good person, but serves bad deeds in a bad person, and good deeds in a good person."(12th) by the end of adolescence, the level of deep awareness will certainly grow significantly. "Humility is the ability to give oneself reasonable happiness, to be critical of oneself and one's behavior.

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